

CFD Analysis of a Two-Phase Fluid Flow Compressor

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Extended Abstract

The goal of the REGEN-BY-2 Horizon 2020 project is to develop a lab-scale prototype of a highly efficient thermodynamic cycle and related plant for the exploitation of renewable thermal energy sources. The whole thermodynamic cycle incorporates Carnot cycles operating with fluid in two-phase flow conditions that circulate through expanders and compressors. The aim of this work is to numerically investigate the two-phase fluid flow in a newly designed two-phase scroll compressor. Numerical simulations represent a reliable tool for the design of Positive Displacement (PD) machines. Therefore, a detailed numerical analysis of a two-phase scroll compressor is necessary for an accurate investigation of the multiphase flow phenomena that occur while the machine is in operation and the finalization of the machine design. To this end, we developed an in-house Cavitating Dynamic Mesh Solver (CDMS) that can predict the phase change phenomena inside the chambers of the compressor. It is a transient cavitation solver based on the Homogeneous Equilibrium Model (HEM) [1] with barotropic closure [2]. The solver considers mesh motion and allows for mesh topology changes. The dynamic grids of the orbiting turbomachine are generated using the OpenFOAM[®] utility *blockMesh* which allows for creating meshes with multiple blocks. The Arbitrary Coupling Mesh Interface (ACMI) is utilized to connect adjacent mesh domains and it is particularly suitable for rotating geometries. The key numerical assessments of the two-phase compressor in the current investigations are the pressure and velocity distribution, liquid evaporation and vapor condensation phenomena, the average inlet and outlet mass flow rates, and the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies. Those are necessary to identify whether the machine is working under overloaded or overheated conditions, or the working fluid causes severe vibrations. The average inlet and outlet mass flow rates, as well as the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies obtained numerically, are in good accordance with the results of a deterministic model (DM) available in the literature [3]. Besides, the distribution of pressure and velocity inside the compressor agrees qualitatively well with the results of numerical studies of scroll compressors available in the literature [4, 5]. The high isentropic and volumetric efficiencies indicate that the investigated compressor type has been well-designed and is capable of efficiently compressing the refrigerant while delivering the desired mass flow rate at the specified pressure and temperature.

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